

Article

Sustainable Leisure, Intergenerational Learning and Grandparents' Level of Education

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Abstract: Sustainable leisure, shared among grandparents and grandchildren, provides multiple benefits, as it enhances contexts and bonds that foster personal, familiar, social and emotional development. In addition to this, it directly contributes to the achievement of the sustainable development goals, established in Agenda 2030. The objective was to examine, from the grandparents' perspective, and taking into account their educational level, the links that exist among co-learning processes and the practice of sustainable intergenerational leisure and its evolution throughout the pandemic era. This project sought to combine quantitative (N = 350) and qualitative (N = 18) methodologies, using an ad hoc questionnaire and a discussion group, in different moments, before and after the pandemic. The SPSS 23.0 statistical program was used for quantitative analysis and the NVivo Release 1.6 software for the qualitative study. The results show that intergenerational co-learning is a motive and a relevant stimulus that encourages both generations to share these experiences in natural spaces, which brings them together and facilitates lifelong learning. It has been proven that, before the lockdown, sustainable leisure practices showed significant differences depending on the level of education of the older generation. This had an impact on participation in activities associated with different types of leisure, with a tendency to increase the practice as the level of education rises. Nevertheless, after the pandemic, a greater reduction has been observed in the practice of shared leisure activities among those with a higher educational level.

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1. Introduction

The environmental dimension of leisure is defined as “a specific manifestation of leisure characterized by the experience of satisfying moments motivated by the context, in the sense of being in a place and/or an environment” [1], and it is linked with nature and outdoor practices, among which travelling, trips, gardening, and animal and plant care are highlighted. All these experiences promote sustainable development, which is one of the main objectives included in Agenda 2030, established by the General Assembly of the United Nations. In addition to contributing to these objectives, environmental leisure practices can be highly beneficial for human development, especially when shared across different generations. Intergenerational relationships are interactions where two or more generations are involved. Family is an ideal context for intergenerational relationships due to the existing bond among its members, the relationships that grandparents and grandchildren have being the most prominent ones [2]. These relations are essential and

evolve throughout a lifetime [3]. With regard to this, intergenerational leisure is defined as those shared experiences among different generations, in this case, grandparents and grandchildren, in which three factors are involved: free choice, intrinsic purpose and a gratifying feeling [4,5]. This results in a leisure activity in which both generations are engaged with the goal of enjoying shared time, feeling satisfaction and happiness, and promoting innovative or creative learning [6].

It is also an ideal context for mutual learning, understood as the creation of new knowledge and updating values, among different people who are committed to learning, sharing and developing their abilities together with others [7]. Then, the focus is on the creation of meanings that go beyond formal education contexts and enable the activation of psycho-emotional processes where each group member commits to their own learning and that of others [8]. The scientific literature highlights that leisure boosts permanent learning when it comes to old people, as it promotes meeting and participation spaces [9], and stimulates the perception of freedom as well as inner motivation, these experiences having been chosen merely because of the pleasure of practicing them [10]. Intergenerational learning develops a reciprocal process in which both the learner and the person who teaches or shows gain from the exchange, and are able to establish collaborative relationships that favor social recognition and identity [11]. In addition to this, intergenerational learning depends on the participants' willingness to cooperate with others in their human development, which gives the opportunity of sharing experiences and carrying out joint activities. Here, the emotional bond between grandparents and grandchildren is a key factor for the mutual learning process [12]. In this sense, it is a reality that, when environmental activities are shared between grandparents and grandchildren, their bond is strengthened. This bond is an enriching, attractive and flexible experience and establishes closer ties and promotes well-being for both generations [13]. They provide multiple benefits at emotional, physical and mental levels, associated with a more active and healthier ageing process [14–16]. Altogether, these experiences promote social interaction, connection with the environment, respectful and proenvironment attitudes, and intergenerational learning and dialogue [17–19]. There are multiple environmental initiatives that grandparents and grandchildren might enjoy together, but family or urban gardens are the ones that stand out due to their capacity to transform the resources, spaces and interpersonal relations management, thereby facilitating intergenerational learning [20], as they include shared activities that foster personal relationships committed and concerned with the environment [21,22]. It is confirmed that the environmental awareness that emerges from intergenerational leisure, when started during childhood, stays with a person for life [23]. Moreover, grandfathers and grandmothers show a greater interest in nature compared to people of other ages, and they obtain personal satisfaction from these experiences, being able to transmit it to younger generations [24–26], the reason why these spaces become ideal contexts for intergenerational exchange within environmental leisure activities.

The COVID-19 pandemic led to a social distance that limited the possibilities of sharing leisure activities and consequently widened the gap with vulnerable groups [27–29]. Family structures and interactions were altered, and leisure activities required restructuring and great adaptation to the new situation, where great limitations affected their development and some of them were even eliminated, given their unfeasibility [29]. Both environmental leisure and intergenerational relations were limited because of these circumstances. Although grandparents are highly present in the lives of their grandchildren and are considered key role models [30–32], interactions between them were affected for fear of contagion and because of the vulnerability of the oldest family members during the pandemic era [33–35]. In this context, technologies became a great learning opportunity for intergenerational learning and approaches [36,37]. Consequently, activities in natural con-

texts were reduced [27], whilst an increase in the exposition and contact with technological devices has been noticed, especially among children, together with worse eating habits or more sedentary routines, even though the families' level of studies has a direct correlation with these lifestyles [38]. Nevertheless, prior findings have proven that nowadays' society has reached a more prosocial and proenvironmental position [39], accompanied by a more favorable sense of responsibility regarding future generations [40,41], these statements being encouraging for the present investigation.

Previous research does not clearly reflect that leisure time shared among grandparents and grandchildren depends on the level of studies of the older group [42], but it confirms that a higher level is associated with higher levels of emotional stress towards caring for grandchildren [43]. This finding seems to be in contradiction with other authors [44,45] who assert that a higher level of educational attainment in old people leads to greater resilience and greater ability to cope with those challenges that may appear when taking care of their grandchildren. Moreover, grandparents with a higher educational level are more likely to dedicate themselves to their grandchildren in order to help parents and provide emotional support [46].

No research has been found that specifically links level of studies to environmental leisure activities shared across generations, and values transmitted to grandchildren. Only authors and research areas related to the importance of family factors for the development of environmental awareness have been identified, which can serve as a foundation for approaching the subject of study from an intergenerational, axiological and ecological perspective. This includes the familial influence to encourage love, care and conservation of the environment from childhood, from home conditions to daily routines [47–49]. Other studies highlight the importance of the intergenerational dialogue for environmental education, which helps reinforce the awareness of both parts, as well as develop and promote respectful values and behaviors towards the environment [50].

The present study aims at examining, from the grandparents' perspective, and according to their level of studies, the connection between mutual learning and the practice of environmental intergenerational leisure, and its evolution within the framework of the pandemic. Analyzing intergenerational relations and their broader implications, particularly within the context of environmental leisure, is of high importance. These dynamics significantly influence social connections across generations, and interactions or experiences with nature, which contribute to sustainability. The analysis of intergenerational relations in environmental leisure contexts offers critical insight into how different age groups interact with nature. The intersections of these relations with environmental leisure remains a largely underexplored area, so this paper is considered a unique and valuable contribution to scientific research. The study seeks to address the gap in the literature by examining how sustainable leisure, intergenerational learning and grandparents' level of education are interconnected, and the impact of the pandemic and lockdown on intergenerational environmental leisure experiences.

This paper proposes the following research question: how does the educational level of grandparents influence the environmental leisure activities they share with their grandchildren, and to what extent does it impact the ecological awareness and sustainable values transmitted to the younger generation? The study is based on the hypotheses that the grandparents' educational level is a crucial factor for the promotion of environmental leisure, because of their potential to influence the type of initiatives they enjoy together, and the environmental sensitivity of the younger generation, as well as the way grandparents transmit ecological values to their grandchildren. This paper will present the materials and methods used to investigate the relationship between generations in the context of environmental leisure, and how the grandparents' educational level affects this dynamic. The

results of the study will then be outlined, providing a detailed analysis of the findings. The discussion will interpret these results, emphasizing the implications of previous research and the significance of the study, and the conclusions will summarize the key insights and suggest directions for future research in this field.

2. Materials and Methods

Both quantitative and qualitative methodologies have been used, through a descriptive-transversal design.

2.1. Participants

In the quantitative stage, the study population was composed of 357 grandfathers and grandmothers of children aged 6–12 years old, living in the north of Spain, including 8 Spanish provinces: Cantabria, Vizcaya, Gipuzkoa, Alava, La Rioja, Navarre, Burgos and Palencia. In an initial phase, the study population was selected after the statistical data published by the Offices and Departments of Education from each autonomous community participating in the study. The data collected showed a population size of 250.357 students of primary education in the north of Spain (Figure 1).

Figure 1. North of Spain (following the Nielsen classification). The selected provinces appear in black.

Setting an absolute error of 3%, a confidence level of 95%, and considering the assumption of $p = q = 0.5$, the sample size was estimated to be 1075 students. With an experimental mortality of 1.11%, the final sample size consisted of 1063 students, from which a sample of 357 grandparents was taken before the pandemic, and 137 after the lockdown, who volunteered to participate in the study. The sample selected after the lockdown belonged to the same group as before the pandemic. The investigators took the data collected in an initial phase to contact them.

A proportion of 2.4% ($n = 12$) of the grandparents do not possess educational qualification, 54.3% ($n = 268$) have completed their primary studies, 25.7% ($n = 127$) secondary studies and 10.9% ($n = 54$) hold higher studies.

A cross-tabulation analysis was conducted with the key variables to compare the homogeneity between the samples before and after the lockdown. Results show that there are no statistically significant differences between the two samples in terms of professional situation, gender, age, family situation and education level. However, a significant difference was detected in the autonomous community variable (Table 1).

Table 1. Cross-tabulation analysis to compare homogeneity pre- and post-pandemic, based on the main demographic and social variables. * indicates statistical significance.

	χ^2	gl	N	Sig.
Professional situation	4.734	3	461	0.192
Gender	0.520	1	493	0.471
Age (4 groups)	7.084	3	467	0.069
Autonomous community	13.105	5	443	0.022 *
Family situation	0.689	2	448	0.708
Education level	4.061	3	461	0.255

In the qualitative phase, participant selection was structural, choosing the composition of the various groups based on membership criteria. Homogeneity was ensured concerning the social group in question (grandparents and grandchildren) and the age of the grandchildren (6–12 years old), as well as the heterogeneity based on gender, number of grandchildren and family type. Apart from this, the study managed the balance of the number of participants, depending on the grandparents' geographical origin (rural or urban setting). The investigation adhered to the recommendations of experts [51] to establish the number of participants in the discussion group, which was made up of 9 grandparents (5 men and 4 women) before the pandemic, and 9 grandparents (6 men and 3 women) after the pandemic.

2.2. Research Instrument

In the quantitative stage, an ad hoc questionnaire was used before and after the lockdown. It was validated through a pilot test applied to 6 school centers of the different autonomous communities and evaluated by a group of 10 experts from seven Spanish universities, who gave positive validation for its final application. The questionnaire enabled the collection of relevant information for this study based on five variables, as can be read below:

1. Leisure activities shared with grandchildren. This is a dichotomous variable that records whether participants share or do not share leisure activities with their grandchildren: travelling, trips, hunting or fishing, animal care, plant care or gardening. Categories are yes/no.
2. Reasons that lead grandparents to share environmental leisure with their grandchildren. This is a categorical variable that gathered the motives and reasons for these practices, giving answers to the question "Name the reason(s) why you share environmental leisure activities" (1 = simply because I like it; 2 = my grandparents take care of me/I take care of my grandchildren while parents are at work; 3 = they are the only people with whom I can share these activities; 4 = they do not have other people to share these activities with; 5 = they know a lot about the activity and they teach me; 6 = I know a lot about the activity and I teach them; 7 = to entertain them; 8 = to spend time together).
3. Level of studies of grandparents. This is a categorical variable that marks the educational attainment of grandparents, through the question: "Mark your level of studies"

(1 = None; 2 = Primary studies (EGB or Primary Education); 3 = Secondary studies (ESO, BUP, Bachillerato, FP); 4 = Higher studies (University).

4. Level of satisfaction associated with shared leisure practices. This is a categorical variable that informed about the grandfathers' and grandmothers' perception of the way that environmental leisure activities shared with grandchildren helps them to be in shape, feel happier, be more creative, develop new manual and/or technical skills, and better interact with their grandchildren. This information is collected along a five-point Likert scale (1 = not satisfied; 5 = very satisfied).
5. Time period of questionnaire administration. The participants of this study answered the questions before and after the lockdown, recording the timing of the response using a dichotomous variable with the following categories: before the lockdown and after the lockdown.

In the qualitative stage, two discussion groups were created composed of grandparents who had grandchildren aged 6–12; one was carried out before the COVID-19 pandemic, and the other one during the post-pandemic period.

The configuration of the category system was based on a theoretical framework about leisure within the context of intergenerational relationships, prior to the transcription evaluation—deductive stage. After this, during the analysis of testimonies, more categories were added and branched into several subcategories—inductive stage. Then, a system of eight general categories and 44 subcategories was created. Table 2 shows the two categories of analysis that are the focus of this study.

The subcategory of analysis under study, environmental leisure, was defined as “activities related to environmental issues and ecology that usually take place outdoors, and in the presence of living beings, such as animals or plants. In this context, natural circumstances, both under wild or outdoors conditions, or contexts linked to the cultivation, breeding or exploitation of living beings for resource extraction, are included”.

Finally, the validation of the system of categories and subcategories of analysis was carried out through expert judgment, achieving positive results [52]. Six university research professors, all of them holding PhDs in the field of Leisure and Pedagogy, acted as experts.

On the one hand, Cohen's Kappa index was used to measure validity, and it indicated the degree of agreement among the main researcher and the rest of experts. The analysis noted a nearly perfect level of agreement with three of the experts (0.862, 0.818 and 0.822) and substantial agreement with the other three (0.742, 0.695 and 0.678).

On the other hand, Fleiss' Kappa Coefficient was calculated to examine the degree of agreement among the experts. It showed a degree of agreement ranging from moderate to very good (between 0.514 and 0.907), so the category validation process was successful (overall score: 0.697).

Table 2. System of categories and subcategories of analysis.

Category 1	Reasons to share leisure activities
Subcategory 1.1	Family feelings
Subcategory 1.2	Time availability
Subcategory 1.3	Entertainment and fun
Subcategory 1.4	Mutual learning
Subcategory 1.5	Mutual help
Subcategory 1.6	Avoiding technological device abuse
Subcategory 1.7	Caregiver's role
Subcategory 1.8	Permissive role

Table 2. Cont.

Category 2	Type of shared leisure activities
Subcategory 2.1	Physical–sport leisure activities
Subcategory 2.2	Recreational leisure activities
Subcategory 2.3	Digital leisure activities
Subcategory 2.4	Environmental–ecological leisure activities
Subcategory 2.5	Cultural leisure activities
Category 4	Places to share leisure activities
Subcategory 4.1	Farm/garden
Subcategory 4.2	Park
Subcategory 4.3	Village
Subcategory 4.4	Home
Subcategory 4.5	Restaurants/cafés
Subcategory 4.6	Lunchroom/dining area
Subcategory 4.7	School center/school environment and facilities
Category 5	Time/period to share leisure activities
Subcategory 5.1	Summer holidays
Subcategory 5.2	Christmas holidays
Subcategory 5.3	Weekends
Subcategory 5.4	Weekdays
Subcategory 5.5	Bank holidays
Subcategory 5.6	Patron saint festivities

Note: adapted from [52].

2.3. Procedure

In the quantitative stage, the questionnaire was administered to the group of grandparents with grandchildren enrolled in the different schools from each of the eight provinces belonging to the north of Spain. Prior to this, the students were given a consent form to deliver to their fathers, mothers or legal guardians, including all the information about the study where they were required to provide the contact details of the grandmother or grandfather willing to participate in the study, to be submitted at the educational center.

Five qualified researchers contacted the grandparents by phone and filled in the questionnaire according to their testimonies. The time taken to record the questions was approximately 30–45 min.

The Ethics Committee of the University of La Rioja approved this procedure. The positive report from the Ethics Committee was registered with the code CE_02_2019.

In the qualitative stage, the same questionnaire protocol both was used in discussion groups (Table 3) and served as a guide, without forgetting the interconnection between the narrative thread and the research objectives along the process [53].

Table 3. Discussion group protocol.

Questions
What type of activities do they usually share with their grandchildren?
What are the reasons to share leisure time with their grandchildren?
Where do these activities usually take place?
When (time/season/holiday/frequency) do they usually share these activities?
What do they get from sharing leisure time with their grandchildren?
What do they provide their grandchildren with when they share leisure activities?

Note: adapted from [52].

At the beginning of the debate, general issues were raised before bringing specific issues into the discussion. These specific issues focused on the analysis of the type of shared leisure activity and, more specifically, on those related to the environment, and the reasons for sharing them with their grandchildren and on the motives that can be associated with mutual learning.

In order to increase reliability, one person acted as a moderator, who was responsible for initiating, maintaining, and guiding the conversation without directly intervening, with the intention of delving into fundamental issues for the present study.

The dialogues were recorded with prior authorization and were literally transcribed afterwards, noting when and who intervened. The discussion groups took approximately one hour.

2.4. Data Analysis

Both quantitative and qualitative methods were included in the investigation, reason that led the investigators to combine SPSS and NVivo for the data analysis. This combination was highly beneficial for the study as it made it possible to carry out an integral analysis. SPSS allowed the investigators to develop a statistical analysis of number and measurable values and statistical trends. On its part, NVivo enabled the organization and analysis to understand the perceptions, experiences and meanings. Thus, the combination of both methodologies has become a common and frequent practice to face the complex phenomenon of social research [54].

Data analysis was conducted using the statistical program SPSS 23.0. A descriptive analysis was carried out and, using frequency statistics, it allowed researchers to learn about the leisure activities that grandparents share with their grandchildren, the type of environmental leisure activities they share and the reasons why they practice them.

Later, an inferential analysis was performed through the Chi-square (χ^2) and H Kruskal–Wallis test, to examine the existence of significant differences between the two moments in time where data were collected (before and after the pandemic), with regard to (a) percentage of grandparents who share leisure time with their grandchildren; (b) percentage of grandparents who share environmental leisure activities with their grandchildren; (c) percentage of grandparents who share different types of environmental leisure activities; (d) reasons to share environmental leisure with their grandchildren; (e) situation of environmental leisure according to the level of studies of the grandparents. The significance level for the entire study was set at $p < 0.05$.

The interpretation of the values in the Kruskal–Wallis test is shown as follows [55]:

- 0. $0 < 0.01$ —Negligible
- 0.01 < 0.04 —Weak
- 0.04 < 0.16 —Moderate
- 0.16 < 0.36 —Relatively strong
- 0.36 < 0.64 —Strong
- 0.64 < 1.00 —Very strong

For qualitative data analysis, NVivo Release 1.6 software was used, which allows for data storage and coding, the creation of memos, notes, etc., the importation of files and documents, and their connection to fragments of the discourses.

3. Results

3.1. Shared Leisure Activities Before and After the Lockdown

During the COVID-19 pandemic, leisure shared between grandparents and grandchildren significantly reduced. This impact was seen in all types of leisure activities, with different degrees of concern. The hierarchy obtained by classifying the types of leisure

according to their level of impact remains relatively stable, cultural and recreational leisure activities being the most common. Environmental leisure activities are in fourth place, both before and after the pandemic, and the most significant change can be seen in festivities and celebrations (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Percentage of people who share leisure activities, before and after the lockdown.

All in all, while three out of four grandparents shared leisure time with their grandchildren before the lockdown, only two out of four do it now, which shows a significant reduction in this practice. When it comes to environmental leisure, the same situation can be appreciated both before and after the pandemic. There was a significant reduction in the number of people who shared this type of leisure after the lockdown (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Percentage of people who share environmental leisure, before and after the lockdown.

3.2. Type of Environmental Activities Shared Among Grandparents and Grandchildren

If environmental leisure activities are analyzed, travelling was the most affected one, with a sharp drop in the number of participants, 44.3% before the lockdown and just 5.8% after the lockdown. However, a slight reduction in the percentage of shared participation in “trips” was obtained. In this sense, more “local” activities, such as “plant care or gardening” and “animal care”, also saw a decrease in participation, but to a lesser extent than “travelling” (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Percentage of people who share different environmental leisure activities, before and after the lockdown.

Altogether, the data show that environmental leisure remains one of the most shared among grandparents and grandchildren from the north of Spain, and the overall reduction is mainly driven by the decrease in travelling and, to a lesser extent, by activities related to animal or plant care. The analysis of the discourse of the discussion groups shows that grandparents share different types of environmental leisure with their grandchildren, as evidenced in the following statements:

I have hens, and when we are at the farm, we keep them inside a square fence. As we have a dog, my grandchildren take them out of the fence with a stick and they look like shepherds, they guide them to their place and shout at the dog “don’t move!”. They give all of them names, this one such and such, the other one so and so. [MAN/76/PRIMARY STUDIES]

They enjoy watching you, I give them nests of the little birds with no eggs, I put some hazelnuts as eggs in autumn, and them parents say that there are no nests anymore, and they say yes, they say that someone’s grandpa brought some, because I’m Jaime’s or Millán’s grandpa there: Millán’s grandpa! They say, they enjoy it, but I enjoy it more with them. [MAN/69/PRIMARY STUDIES]

3.3. Level of Studies and Environmental Leisure

If we delve into the situation of shared environmental leisure depending on the educational level, it can be stated that the differences go from being significant (with a clear tendency to increase the practice as level of educational attainment rises) to not being significant after the lockdown, when the differences among people with primary education and people with higher education also disappear (Table 4).

Regarding the activities that belong to the category of environmental leisure, the same results are obtained. While in the period prior to COVID-19 there was a clear bias according to the level of education, after the lockdown this association is no longer significant largely because of the low number of samples collected, motivated by the general reduction in the practice of shared leisure (Figures 5 and 6).

Table 4. Percentage of people who practice environmental leisure according to their level of studies before and after the pandemic. * indicates statistical significance.

		None	Primary Education	Secondary Education	Higher Education	Total
Ecological–environmental leisure *	Before	60.0	74.9	81.8	91.7	78.1
Ecological–environmental leisure	After	50.0	57.9	57.1	44.4	55.2

Figure 5. Environmental leisure activities according to the level of studies before the pandemic. * indicates statistical significance.

Figure 6. Environmental leisure activities according to the level of studies after the pandemic. * indicates statistical significance.

The reasons to share this type of leisure are not associated with the educational level of grandparents, but there is a clear reduction in people who share these activities with the purpose of entertaining their grandchildren (Table 5).

Table 5. Reasons to share environmental leisure according to the level of studies before and after the pandemic.

	None		Primary Education		Secondary Education		Higher Education		Total	
	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A
I like it	100.0	0.0	80.1	58.3	84.4	100.0	79.3	63.6	81.7	67.8
To spend more time together	100.0	0.0	76.8	58.3	74.0	75.0	69.0	45.5	75.7	59.3
To entertain them	100.0	0.0	60.3	27.8	67.5	16.7	69.0	36.4	64.3	27.1
I take care of them while parents work	16.7	0.0	25.2	25.0	27.3	8.3	20.7	18.2	25.1	20.3
I know this activity and I teach them	16.7	0.0	23.2	16.7	20.8	25.0	41.4	27.3	24.3	20.3
Other reasons	0.0	0.0	2.0	5.6	1.3	0.0	6.9	0.0	2.3	3.4
They do not have other people to practice this activity with	0.0	0.0	0.7	2.8	5.2	8.3	0.0	0.0	1.9	3.4
My grandson/granddaughter teaches me	0.0	0.0	3.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.9	0.0
I do not have other people to practice this activity with	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.0	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0

The qualitative analysis shows that mutual learning is highly present in the grandparents' speeches when it comes to reasons that boost the practice of environmental leisure activities.

I built a rock wall in my village. One day, my grandchildren come and they see the concrete mixer. . . There was no way to take them away from there. And they still dream of the mixer. You can't imagine the pictures braking pedals, turning around. . . They love it. And the youngest granddaughter moved just like me. [MAN/76/PRIMARY STUDIES]

At the garden I teach him everything I can, picking tomatoes. . . [MAN/74/UNIVERSITY STUDIES]

My little 6-year-old grandson was planting onions one day. I make the furrow and then I place the onions. And you take them. And he says: grandpa, I help you. For each hole, you put one little onion. And they love helping you. And then I take the mechanical mule to till the land—it's bigger than him, and he goes tilling with it. [MAN/70/NO STUDIES]

I used to have livestock, and my grandchildren used to take care of the animals with me. They learned how to milk and make cheese. I'd put them a cap. I taught them everything and we had lots of work with four grandchildren. And they were so happy. They used to come with me since they were very young. I have pictures of them making cheese. And they remember it. What a pity I do not have them now. [WOMAN/65/PRIMARY STUDIES]

In my village I love that grandchildren learn about everything. About the garden, for instance. This cannot be done in cities. They love to learn. [WOMAN/72/PRIMARY STUDIES]

When examining the level of well-being associated with the practice of shared environmental leisure, opinions were similar among people with different levels of educational attainment and there was no statistical association, before the pandemic. Nevertheless, once the situation returned to normal, people with higher and lower level of studies seem to feel significantly less satisfied (Table 6).

Table 6. Perceived well-being in the practice of shared environmental leisure before and after the pandemic, according to level of studies. * indicates statistical significance.

		Before		After	
		Average Range	Statistical Data H Kruskal–Wallis Test	Average Range	Statistical Data H Kruskal–Wallis Test
It helps me keep in shape	None	171.5	H = 2.347 $p = 0.504$ $\epsilon^2 = 0.01$	14.5 *	H = 9.364 $p = 0.025$ $\epsilon^2 = 0.09$
	Primary education	174.4		59.0 *	
	Secondary education	182.7		50.5 *	
	Higher education	193.0		42.2 *	
It helps me feel happier	None	175.0	H = 3.446 $p = 0.328$ $\epsilon^2 = 0.01$	56.5 *	H = 9.579 $p = 0.023$ $\epsilon^2 = 0.09$
	Primary education	177.3		56.5 *	
	Secondary education	176.4		48.9 *	
	Higher education	192.5		47.9 *	
It helps me be more creative	None	185.3	H = 2.401 $p = 0.493$ $\epsilon^2 = 0.01$	45.3	H = 7.637 $p = 0.054$ $\epsilon^2 = 0.07$
	Primary education	173.0		60.0	
	Secondary education	186.3		45.1	
	Higher education	187.5		44.1	
It helps me to develop new manual and/or technical skills	None	184.2	H = 3.940 $p = 0.268$ $\epsilon^2 = 0.01$	27.0 *	H = 8.087 $p = 0.044$ $\epsilon^2 = 0.08$
	Primary education	172.5		59.9 *	
	Secondary education	181.2		45.7 *	
	Higher education	199.7		45.4 *	
It helps me build better relationships with my grandchild(ren)	None	157.8	H = 2.210 $p = 0.530$ $\epsilon^2 = 0.01$	59.5	H = 2.501 $p = 0.475$ $\epsilon^2 = 0.02$
	Primary education	178.8		54.9	
	Secondary education	177.8		51.8	
	Higher education	184.3		48.2	

Before the pandemic, no statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were found in any of the well-being dimensions evaluated according to educational level. The average ranks showed relatively similar values across different educational levels, suggesting homogeneity in the perception of well-being regardless of academic background.

However, after the pandemic, significant differences ($p < 0.05$) emerged in three key dimensions: “It helps me keep in shape” ($H = 9.364, p = 0.025, \epsilon^2 = 0.09$); “It helps me feel happier” ($H = 9.579, p = 0.023, \epsilon^2 = 0.09$); and “It helps me to develop new manual and/or technical skills” ($H = 8,087, p = 0.044, \epsilon^2 = 0.08$). These differences are not only statistically significant but also exhibit an effect size (ϵ^2) that can be considered moderate according to standard criteria.

This change could be attributed, in part, to an increase in emotional stress in certain educational groups, which affected the evaluation and practice of these activities. It should also be taken into account when interpreting this result that, as mentioned earlier, the difference that existed in the incidence of nature-based leisure activities between people of different educational levels has disappeared. The post-pandemic analysis reveals a consistent and notable pattern: grandparents with primary education consistently show higher average ranks (59.0 *, 56.5 *, 60.0, 59.9 *) compared to those with secondary education (50.5 *, 48.9 *, 45.1, 45.7 *) and, especially, those with higher education (42.2 *, 47.9 *, 44.1, 45.4 *). These results suggest that, after the pandemic, grandparents with lower educational levels (particularly those with primary education) perceive greater benefits in terms of physical well-being, emotional well-being and skill development when engaging in environmental leisure activities.

4. Discussion

The pandemic has brought about a significant reduction in shared leisure among grandparents and grandchildren [27–29]. Leisure activities that take place in natural environments are usually shared among grandparents and grandchildren. Natural spaces have become exceptional contexts to share intergenerational leisure activities, although contact time among generations reduced due to the pandemic and these practices had to adapt to the new circumstances [29]. This is the case of travelling together. Travel restrictions and the uncertainty regarding the pandemic might have discouraged grandparents and grandchildren from travelling together. Nevertheless, this study states a small reduction in joint participation when it comes to trips, which makes us understand that nearby excursions that represent environmental leisure activities remain. Subsequently, the reductions in travel are probably connected to the limitations and insecurities concerning the pandemic [27–29]. On the other hand, activities such as gardening have become excellent leisure options, and they have been established as leisure spaces, frequented by grandparents and grandchildren for their shared environmental intergenerational activities.

Regarding the reasons to share environmental leisure, the results showed that this type of practice strengthens emotional ties and allows the reciprocal transmission of knowledge [20]. For grandparents, transmitting knowledge to their grandchildren in natural contexts is of high importance, as it is their preference and love for their village, the countryside and gardens [24]. In contrast with this, the number of people who practice these activities to entertain their grandchildren has decreased significantly after the pandemic. Older people perceive that they are mainly the ones who teach something in most of the activities shared [40], except for those related to digital leisure. Environmental leisure experiences take place in spaces that enhance the exchange of knowledge, the creation of meanings in a participatory way and the development of certain skills concerning the environment, which brings about intergenerational learning and consequently provides well-being to all participants [7,8].

When analyzing the main variable of the study, which is the educational level of the older generation, our findings show that, before the pandemic, the educational attainment of grandparents had an influence over participation in shared environmental leisure activities, with a trend towards increasing the practice as the educational level rises, in line with other research [44,45]. However, after the pandemic, people with higher educational level are the ones who have reduced their shared practice of environmental activities, which may be associated with higher levels of emotional stress [43]. The results of the statistical tests, particularly the Kruskal–Wallis analysis, show that the educational level of grandparents has become a determining factor in the perception of well-being derived from environmental leisure activities shared with their grandchildren, particularly after the pandemic. The finding of statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) with medium effect sizes (ϵ^2 between 0.08 and 0.09) in key dimensions such as physical well-being, emotional well-being and skill development suggests that, after the health crisis, grandparents with higher educational levels have not managed to recover the perceived benefits of these intergenerational interactions to the same degree as other grandparents, especially those with primary education. This notably contrasts with the pre-pandemic situation, where the educational level was not a significant differentiating factor.

The present investigation confirms that, before the pandemic, the perception of satisfaction towards environmental leisure was similar among all grandparents, regardless of their educational attainment. But, as soon as normality returned, people with higher and lower level of studies perceived less satisfaction with this practice. This finding seems broadly consistent with previous research [43], as it linked a higher educational level of grandparents to higher emotional stress when caring for grandchildren.

Social desirability is one of the limitations of the study and it might have influenced the grandparents' replies regarding their leisure experiences when shared with their grandchildren [56]. As a prospective study and given the difficulties that arise from the pandemic, as it caused emotional problems in terms of loneliness, sadness, disappointment or longing for past times, especially among old people [29,33], it is necessary to promote intergenerational leisure as a stimulus to alleviate this situation. Previous studies state that urban policy makers and environmental agents should apply design and management strategies to natural spaces from a sustainable perspective, in order to promote intergenerational cohesion within these spaces [57,58]. This approach would not only enhance the interaction and connection between generations, but also contribute to the development of a shared environmental awareness. Public policies should prioritize the creation of accessible and engaging environments for all ages to make it possible for grandparents and grandchildren to count on spaces that allow an active participation in leisure experiences.

Similarly, there is a need for greater family education, as it has been found that families are insufficiently prepared to educate children in terms of sustainability values [59]. Therefore, this investigation suggests that it is crucial to develop educational programs that involve families and sustainability, throughout effective and innovative methods that help transmit these values to younger generations. In addition to this, once the benefits of shared environmental leisure have been proven, and due to the stronger presence of technologies within the framework of leisure at home since the pandemic began [60], as well as their fundamental role in relation to environmental leisure activities and mutual learning derived from them [36,37], the study's future approach is to investigate the contribution of technologies in environmental leisure shared among grandparents and grandchildren. The study suggests analyzing the role of apps, augmented and virtual reality, portable and wearable devices, digital maps and tours, environmental videogames, digital cameras and drones, among others. Multiple benefits have been seen when grandparents and grandchildren enjoy nature and natural environments together, so it is necessary to continue this line of investigation.

In summary, the findings of this study have significant implications for the design of public policies and educational programs. Greater preparation and awareness about sustainability can significantly contribute to the promotion of ecological values and strengthen intergenerational cohesion, which demonstrates the potential of the research, and the practical implications in real-world contexts.

5. Conclusions

As commented above, the pandemic led to a reduction in shared leisure across generations. This is the case with all types of leisure activities, although with different degrees of impact. The reduction observed in the percentage of people who share environmental leisure does not stand out significantly compared to other types of leisure, as it shows a decrease in frequency that is similar to that shown by more widespread or common types of leisure, such as cultural or recreational. Thus, it cannot be confirmed that the situation of environmental leisure is inherently tied to its definition. The most drastic decrease can be seen in festive leisure or celebrations.

Environmental leisure is of great interest to promote intergenerational relationships, despite the fact that the pandemic has considerably reduced meetings between generations, in line with other types of leisure. In this study it can be concluded that a higher educational level of grandparents led to a reduction in the shared practice of environmental activities after the pandemic. Along with this statement, after the pandemic, a higher educational level of grandparents results in a reduction in the shared practice of environmental activities, such as travelling. However, excursions to nearby places or gardening experiences have

been a key part of this type of leisure. Apart from this, the grandparents' level of studies does not have a clear impact on the motivations for the practice of environmental leisure activities shared with their grandchildren. Moreover, in relation to satisfaction with shared environmental leisure, the grandparents' educational level influenced this perception after the pandemic.

Regarding the motivations behind shared environmental leisure activities, our investigation points out that the reasons remain stable both before and after the pandemic, regardless of the level of studies of the older group. Particularly noteworthy is that the main reason for grandparents to share environmental leisure is because they like it and because they want to spend more time with their grandchildren.

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